
Public-Private Partnership in Housing Provision in Abuja, Federal Capital Territory (F. C. T)

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Abstract Housing projects beyond shelter to include the group of neighbourhood services and facilities that make the structure for human's habitation; liveable. Provision of housing has been a major challenge confronting all (either developed and/or developing) nations. Public-private partnership has been evident to be advantageous major model of combating the challenges of housing deficit worldwide. This paper assess the structures and strategies employed in provision of housing in Abuja F. C. T. through public-private partnership. From the questionnaires administered and retrieved, it was discovered that there is very strong coefficient magnitude of relationship between the PPP structures and PPP strategies in Abuja, F. C. T.

Keywords Housing Provision, Public-Private Partnership, Structures and Strategies

Introduction

Housing is the core of many socio-economic activities. Ownership of housing is a denotation of some physic income [1], prosperity, social acceptance, and an element of urban development and growth [2]; [3]; [4]. The accessibility and availability of decent housing for each family expresses each country's level of development; as housing is a fundamental issue for people in all corners of the world [5]. It is generally believed that the well-being of every individual is enhanced by the total level of enjoyment of certain standards of living condition [6]. Globally, provision of an affordable housing is a major challenge facing all and sundry in all facets of life. It is pertinent that both developed and developing countries of the world are witnessing a high demand for housing and urban development projects beyond the capacity of the public sector [7] and it is anticipated that about 3 billion people or roughly 40 per cent of the world's population will lack proper housing by 2030 [8]. In Nigeria, poor governance systems, human resource deficiencies, as well as poor institutions' guidelines and regulations have necessitated limited supply of housing. Unprecedentedly, the scale of housing crisis in Nigeria is alarming as Nigeria builds about 600,000 fewer homes than are needed, adding to the current dearth of 23 million that has been growing for decades [9].

Therefore, novel strategies that involve collaboration with the private sector are needed to help governments cope with the growing demand [10], which consequently, made many states to adopt Public-Private Partnership (PPP) as an alternative strategy for the provision of housing and infrastructure [11]; [12]. Public-private partnership involves long-term collaboration between public and private sectors in which the collaborating actors mutually agree to share risks, costs and benefits in the development of products or services [13].

There are many public-private partnerships models in housing provision, which are all embraced by direct and indirect real estate developers. These models of PPP in housing provision includes Build-Operate-Transfer (BOT), Build Own Operate (BOO), Build-Develop-Operate (BDO), Build-Lease-Operate-Transfer (BLOT), Build-Own-Operate-Transfer (BOOT), Buy-Build-Operate (BBO), Contract Services Operations and

Maintenance, Design Build Maintain Operate (DBFMO), Design-Build-Operate (DBO), Design-Build-Finance-Operate (DBFO), Design-Build-Maintain (DBM), Design-Build-Operate (DBO), Design-Construct-Management-Finance (DCMF), Developer Finance, Enhanced Use Leasing (EUL), Lease Purchase, Lease/Develop/Operate (LDO), Operate-Under-License (OL), Operations, Maintenance, & Management, Sale and leaseback, Tax-exempt Lease and Turnkey [14]; [15]; [16]; [17].

The rationale for establishing these models of partnership for housing provision is ensuring that both the private and public sectors tap the distinct advantages for housing provision for the masses thereby reducing the gap and deficits in housing provision. This paper however, assesses models public-private partnership in housing provision in Abuja, Federal Capital Territory (F.C.T) with a view of determining the most efficient PPP model for Abuja, (F. C. T) and other similar cities.

Materials and Methods

Design and setting

The research design was survey research and the primary sources of data were employed. A set of questionnaire (with close-ended, open-ended and Likert-scale questions) was as the instrument for data collection. Snowball sampling technique was employed because population of Real Estate Developers in Abuja, F. C. T are countable and hidden.

Sample/participants

The target population included all members of Real Estate Developers in Abuja, Federal Capital Territory. According to Federal Ministry of Power, Housing and Land Abuja, the total number of valid real estate developers in Abuja in 2021 is 182. This comprises of both direct and indirect real estate developers and they constitute the sample frame for this research. The sample sizes for this academic paper work is 73. They were gotten through snowball sampling technique, which represents 40.56% of the sample frame for an assessment of models public-private partnership in housing provision in Abuja, F. C. T.

The inclusion criteria encompassed public real estate developers (also known as indirect real estate developers) in Abuja F. C. T. and private real estate developers (also known as direct real estate developers) in Abuja F. C. T.

Data collection

Pilot survey was conducted to ensure data reliability and data validity. Data reliability was conducted using retest method of 10 questionnaires. In this retest method, five (5) questionnaires were first shared to Private and Public Real Estate Developers in Abuja, F.C.T. and retrieved, while the same five (5) Private and Public Real Estate Developers in Abuja, F. C. T. were re-shared another new questionnaires the identical content to the earlier ones. These questionnaires comprised of open-ended questions, which gave the researcher the opportunity of discovering the responses and suggestions that are new to the researcher (Foddy, 1993). In ensuring accuracy and meaningfulness of inferences of the questionnaire used as instrument for data collection, the researchers made four (4) copies of the proposed questionnaire available to four (4) professionals in the field of real estate to assess the worthiness of the questionnaire before pilot survey and research survey. All the observations were effected before the questionnaire was administered for the pilot and field survey. All the observations were effected before the questionnaire was administered for the pilot and field survey.

Ethical concern was also given a priority by ensuring that data gotten were strictly for academic purposes, avoidance of ambiguous questions and none of the administered questionnaires has means of identity, which makes all respondents remain confidential and anonymous throughout to avoid any problem that may be detrimental to these Private and Public Real Estate Developers in Abuja, F. C. T.

Statistical analysis

Data were analysed via Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25 using descriptive statistics (frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation) and inferential statistics (correlation).

Results and Discussion

Results**Table 1:** Public-Private Partnerships' structures in housing provision in Nigeria

Public-Private Partnership Structures	Mean	Standard Deviation	Rank
Turnkey	3.5294	1.32113	1
Sale/leaseback	3.4559	1.01384	2
Operate-Under-License (OL)	3.2941	1.18522	3
Build-Operate-Transfer (BOT)	3.2353	1.45702	4
Build-Develop-Operate (BDO)	3.0441	1.33197	5
Operations Maintenance and Management	3.0294	1.29258	6
Lease purchase	3.0294	1.25746	7
Design build operate	3.0000	1.26962	8
Design-Build-Finance-Operate (DBFO)	2.9265	1.18845	9
Lease/develop/operate (LDO)	2.9118	1.15559	10
Design-Construct-Manage-Finance (DCMF)	2.9118	1.14260	11
Tax-exempt lease	2.8824	1.15293	12
Build own operate (BOO)	2.8235	1.35978	13
Design Build Finance Maintain Operate (DBFMO)	2.8088	1.26086	14
Build-Own-Operate-Transfer (BOOT)	2.7794	1.34770	15
Buy-Build-Operate (BBO)	2.7353	1.38884	16
Design-Build-Maintain (DBM)	2.7059	1.32776	17
Contract Services Operations and Maintenance	2.6618	1.25318	18
Design-build-operate (DBO)	2.6471	1.10311	19
Build-Lease-Operate-Transfer (BLOT)	2.6029	1.25947	20
Developer Finance	2.5882	1.18744	21
Enhanced Use Leasing (EUL)	2.2500	1.07029	22

Source: Field Survey, (2021).

The table above shows Public-Private Partnerships' structures in housing provision in Nigeria. Turnkey, sale/leaseback, Operate-Under-License, Built-Operate-Transfer, Build-Develop-Operate (BDO) and Operations Maintenance and Management have a mean score of 3.5294 with standard deviation of 1.32113, mean score of 3.4559 with standard deviation of 1.01384, mean score of 3.2941 with standard deviation of 1.18522, mean score of 3.2353 with standard deviation of 1.45702, mean score of 3.0441 with standard deviation of 1.33197 and mean score of 3.0294 with standard deviation of 1.29258 respectively.

Also, Lease purchase, Design Build Operate, Design-Build-Finance-Operate (DBFO), Lease/develop/operate (LDO), Design-Construct-Manage-Finance (DCMF), Tax-exempt lease, Build Own Operate (BOO), Design Build Finance Maintain Operate (DBFMO) and Build-Own-Operate-Transfer (BOOT) have a mean score of 3.0294 with standard deviation of 1.25746, mean score of 3.0000 with standard deviation of 1.26962, mean score of 2.9265 with standard deviation of 1.18845, mean score of 2.9118 with standard deviation of 1.15559, mean score of 2.9118 with standard deviation of 1.14260, mean score of 2.8824 with standard deviation of 1.15293, mean score of 2.8235 with standard deviation of 1.35978, mean score of 2.8088 with standard deviation of 1.26086 and mean score of 2.7794 with standard deviation of 1.34770 respectively.

However, Buy-Build-Operate (BBO), Design-Build-Maintain (DBM), Contract Services Operations and Maintenance, Design-build-operate (DBO), Build-Lease-Operate-Transfer (BLOT), Developer Finance and Enhanced Use Leasing (EUL) have a mean score of 2.7353 with standard deviation of 1.38884, mean score of 2.7059 with standard deviation of 1.32776, mean score of 2.6618 with standard deviation of 1.25318, mean score of 2.6471 with standard deviation of 1.10311, mean score of 2.6029 with standard deviation of 1.25947, mean score of 2.5882 with standard deviation of 1.18744 and mean score of 2.2500 with standard deviation of 1.07029 respectively.

Table 2: The Strategies adopted in Public-Private Partnerships for affordable housing provision in Abuja, F. C. T.

Strategies	Mean	Standard Deviation	Rank
Collaboration with communities in housing schemes development	3.5000	1.07203	1
The removal of any regulatory obstacles in PPP arrangement	3.2941	1.00831	2
Identifying potential resources in private sector for PPP arrangement	3.0147	0.98485	3
Developing operational guidelines and tools for PPP projects by both partners	3.0000	1.25781	4
Matching the expertise from both partners	2.8529	1.37423	5
The public sector provides the performance specifications for the Private sector to design and build	2.8529	0.91854	6
The creation of broad public and political support for PPP	2.6765	1.37614	7
Transfer of public sector tasks to private partners for a period (Design-Build-Finance-Maintain-Operate (DBFMO))	2.5882	1.06834	8
Provision of funds by the public sector for the private sector to execute the project	2.5882	0.96561	9
Risk sharing between private and public sectors in housing delivery	2.5294	1.27514	10
The private sector constructs and finances the capital cost of an asset for the public sector to operate	2.5147	1.23980	11
Developing PPP projects and managing capacity of both partners	2.2941	0.75427	12
The private sector uses equity funds to finance housing schemes while the public sector supervises the execution of the housing scheme	2.2059	1.08667	13

Source: Field Survey, (2021).

Table 2 shows strategies adopted in Public-Private Partnerships for affordable housing provision in Abuja, F. C. T. Collaboration with communities in housing schemes development has a mean score of 3.5000 and a standard deviation of 1.07203. Removal of any regulatory obstacles in PPP arrangement, Identifying potential resources in private sector for PPP arrangement and Developing operational guidelines and tools for PPP projects by both partners have a mean score of 3.2941 with standard deviation of 1.00831, mean score of 3.0441 with standard deviation of 1.17732, mean score of 3.0147 with standard deviation of 0.98485 and a mean score of 3.0000 with standard deviation of 1.25781 respectively.

Also, Matching the expertise from both partners, The public sector provides the performance specifications for the Private sector to design and build, The creation of broad public and political support for PPP, Transfer of public sector tasks to private partners for a period (Design-Build-Finance-Maintain-Operate (DBFMO)), Provision of funds by the public sector for the private sector to execute the project, Risk sharing between private and public sectors in housing delivery, The private sector constructs and finances the capital cost of an asset for the public sector to operate, Developing PPP projects and managing capacity of both partners and the private sector uses equity funds to finance housing schemes while the public sector supervises the execution of the housing scheme have a mean score of 2.8529 with standard deviation of 1.37423, mean score of 2.8529 with standard deviation of 0.91854, mean score of 2.6765 with standard deviation of 1.37614, mean score of 2.5882 with standard deviation of 1.06834, mean score of 2.5882 with standard deviation of 0.96561, mean score of 2.5294 with standard deviation of 1.27514, mean score of 2.5147 with standard deviation of 1.23980, mean score of 2.2941 with standard deviation of 0.75427 and mean score of 2.2059 with standard deviation of 1.08667 respectively.

Table 3: Public-Private Partnerships' structures and strategies adopted in Public-Private Partnerships for affordable housing provision in Abuja, F. C. T

Correlations		Services	Methods
Structures	Pearson Correlation	1	0.965**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000
	N	68	68
Strategies	Pearson Correlation	0.965**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	
	N	68	68

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

The Table 3 gives analysis of the magnitude of relationship between public-private partnerships' structures and strategies adopted in public-private partnerships for affordable housing provision in Abuja, F. C. T using Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient. This Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient result as shown in Table 3 is 0.965. The magnitude of relationships specified in descriptors of Burris (2005), indicated that magnitudes of relationship with coefficients >0.69 is Very Strong, 0.50 to 0.69 is Substantial, 0.30 to 0.49 is Moderate, 0.10 to 0.29 as weak while 0.01 to 0.09 is Negligible. In line with the descriptors of Burris [18], magnitude of relationship between public-private partnerships' structures and strategies adopted in public-private partnerships for affordable housing provision in Abuja, F. C. T using Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient is Very Strong.

Discussion

It was discovered that the major Public-Private Partnerships' structures in housing provision in Abuja, F. C. T. are Turnkey, Sale/leaseback, Operate-Under-License, Built-Operate-Transfer, Build-Develop-Operate and Operations Maintenance and Management and they were ranked the 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th, 5th and the 6th structures respectively. This is dissimilar to the finding of Oyedele [19] that stated that the major public-private partnership structures in Nigeria are Design and Build, Turnkey Project, Contract Management and Direct Labour of traditional method. While Oyeniya [20] opined that the major public-private partnership structures for housing provision are Turnkey, Sale/leaseback, Operate-Under-License, Built-Operate-Transfer, Build-Develop-Operate and Operations Maintenance and Management. The opinion of Oyeniya [20] is sustained.

Meanwhile, the major strategies adopted in public-private partnerships for affordable housing provision in Abuja, F. C. T. includes collaboration with communities in housing schemes development, removal of any regulatory obstacles in PPP arrangement, identifying potential resources in private sector for PPP arrangement; and developing operational guidelines and tools for PPP projects by both partners. This is buttress the similar findings of Ojebode [9].

However, the coefficient of magnitude of relationship between public-private partnerships' structures and strategies adopted in public-private partnerships for affordable housing provision in Abuja, F. C. T using Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient is very strong. This is not the same with the findings of Yahaya, Ibrahim and Hariati [21] that submitted that relationship between public-private partnerships' structures and strategies adopted in public-private partnerships for affordable housing provision in Abuja, F. C. T is strong. Nonetheless the findings of this research is sustained.

Conclusion

This academic paper attempts were made to assess models of public-private partnership in housing provision in Abuja, Federal Capital Territory (F. C. T). The data collected and analysed revealed that there is a very strong coefficient of magnitude of relationship between public-private partnerships' structures and strategies adopted in public-private partnerships for affordable housing provision in Abuja, F. C. T.

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Appendix

Questionnaire

(Real Estate Developers)

1. Please indicate your gender

- (a.) Male [] (b.) Female []

2. Please kindly indicate your position in your firm

- a.) Principal Partner [] (b) Partner [] (c.) Associate Partner [] (d.) Head of Department []
(e.) Property/Facility Manager [] (f.) Builder [], (g) Consultant []

3. Please kindly indicate your institution

- (a.) Private or Direct Real Estate Developer [] (b.) Public or Indirect Real Estate Developer []

4. Please tick your age

- (a.) 30 Years and below [], (b) 31-40years [] (c.) 41-50years [], (d.) 51-60years []
(e.) 61 and above []

5. What is your highest level of qualification

- (a.) ND [], (b.) HND [], (c.) First Degree [], (d.) Master [], (e.) PhD []

6. Year of graduation

- (a.) Less than 5 years [], (b) 6-10 years [] (c.) 11 -15 years [], (d.) 16 -20 years []
(e.) 21 -25 years [], (f.) 26 -30 years [], (g) Over 30 years []

7. Years of Working after graduation

- (a.) Less than 5 years [], (b) 6-10 years [] (c.) 11 -15 years [], (d.) 16 -20 years []
(e.) 21 -25 years [], (f.) 26 -30 years [], (g) Over 30 years []

8. Years of working with real estate development firm

- (a.) Less than 5 years [], (b) 6-10 years [] (c.) 11 -15 years [], (d.) 16 -20 years []
(e.) 21 -25 years [], (f.) 26 -30 years [], (g) Over 30 years []

9. How long have you been with this institution?

- (a.) Less than 5 years [], (b) 6-10 years [] (c.) 11 -15 years [], (d.) 16 -20 years []
(e.) 21 -25 years [], (f.) 26 -30 years [], (g) Over 30 years []

10. How often are you aware of the following structures of Public-Private Partnership in Nigeria **5= Always, 4= Often, 3 = Sometimes, 2=Rarely and 1= Never.**

S/N	Structures	Always 5	Often 4	Sometimes 3	Rarely 2	Never 1
a.	Build-Operate-Transfer (BOT)					
b.	Build own operate (BOO)					
c.	Build-Develop-Operate (BDO)					
d.	Build-Lease-Operate-Transfer (BLOT)					

e.	Build-Own-Operate-Transfer (BOOT)					
f.	Buy-Build-Operate (BBO)					
g.	Contract services operations and maintenance					
h.	Design Build Maintain Operate (DBFMO)					
i.	Design-Build-Operate (DBO)					
j.	Design-Build-Finance-Operate (DBFO)					
k.	Design-build-maintain (DBM)					
l.	Design-build-operate (DBO)					
m.	Design-Construct-Manage-Finance (DCMF)					
n.	Developer finance					
o.	Enhanced use leasing (EUL)					
p.	Lease purchase					
q.	Lease/develop/operate (LDO)					
r.	Operate-Under-License (OL)					
s.	Operations, maintenance, & management					
t.	Sale and leaseback					
u.	Tax-exempt lease					
v.	Turnkey					
Others (Please Write)						
w.						
x.						
y.						
z.						

11. How would you rate the effectiveness of the following strategies in the adoption of PPP in affordable housing delivery in Abuja? Kindly use the scale: **5= Very Effective, 4= Effective, 3 = Moderate, 2=Less Effective and 1= Not Effective,**

S/N	Strategies	Very Effective 5	Effective 4	Moderate 3	Less Effective 2	Not Effective 1
a.	Involvement of experts inputs from both the private and the public sectors					
b.	Provision of funds by the public sector for the private sector to execute the project					
c.	Collaboration with communities in housing schemes development					
d.	Risk sharing between private and public sectors in housing delivery					
f.	The public sector provides the performance specifications for the Private sector to design and build					
g.	The private sector uses equity funds to finance housing schemes while the public sector supervises the execution of the housing scheme					
h.	The private sector constructs and finances the capital cost of an asset for the public sector to operate					
i.	Transfer of public sector tasks to private partners for a period (Design-Build-Finance-Maintain-Operate (DBFMO))					
j.	Developing operational guidelines and tools for PPP projects					

	by both partners					
k.	Developing PPP projects and managing capacity of both partners.					
l.	The removal of any regulatory obstacles in PPP arrangement					
m.	The creation of broad public and political support for PPP					
n.	Identifying potential resources in private sector for PPP arrangement					
o.	Identifying potential development companies for PPP arrangement					
p.	Matching the expertise from both partners					
If others (Please Specify)						
q.						
r.						
s.						
t.						
u.						
v.						

Thank you so much for taking your valuable time in answering this questionnaire.

